

Beauty of Magic Squares: 3888-Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 144 - Part 4

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The work is also available at author's site:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=18745>

Abstract

*This paper presents a systematic construction of **multiple order bordered magic squares** at orders 12, 20, 30, 42, 56, 72, 90, 110, 132 and 144. (for a full structural summary). Unlike classical block-wise bordered magic squares, which are built as multiples of a single block size, the structures explored here incorporate successive borders drawn from magic squares of **different** orders — specifically orders 3 through 11 — each contributing a distinct structural layer. To bring order 144, order 6 is applied over order 132, and order 11 is used over 90 to bring order 132. The magic squares orders are considered as 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 6. In some cases, **even-order borders** consist of **equal-sum**, while **odd-order borders** consist of **different-sum** magic squares. In some cases, the even orders are also considered with different magic sums. The combinatorial multiplicity of border types at each level yields a hierarchy of distinct configurations.*

Keywords: magic squares, bordered magic squares, **pandiagonal** magic squares, multiple order borders, combinatorial enumeration, recreational mathematics.

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1 Introduction

A **magic square** of order n is an arrangement of n^2 distinct integers in an $n \times n$ grid such that the sums of each row, each column, and both main diagonals are equal. This common value is called the **magic constant** (or magic sum), usually denoted S . For a magic square containing the consecutive integers $1, 2, \dots, n^2$, the magic constant is

$$S = \frac{n(n^2 + 1)}{2}. \tag{1}$$

Magic squares have fascinated mathematicians, artists, and philosophers for millennia, appearing in ancient texts. Two constructions are central to the present work.

Definition 1.1 (Bordered magic square). *A magic square is said to be **bordered** if the removal of any outermost border of cells leaves a smaller magic square. All entries are consecutive integers.*

Definition 1.2 (Block-wise bordered magic square). *A magic square is **block-wise bordered** if each border layer is not a single cell wide but is composed of smaller magic squares used as building blocks.*

During past years author [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10] worked with **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 47. Author [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16] also worked with **bordered** magic squares. The study on **bordered** magic squares is extended to **block-bordered** magic squares [17, 18, 19]. This is specially done for the magic squares of orders p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. This study is still extended to **block-wise bordered** magic squares [20, 21, 22, 23]. Some connection with Pythagorean triples and area-representations are also made [25, 26, 27, 28, 29]. The main property of **bordered** magic squares is that if we remove external borders, still we get **sub-bordered** magic squares, i.e., each layer in itself lead us to magic squares. In many cases, the properties of **bordered** magic square are separated by **even** and **odd** orders magic squares. In many cases, we get good properties for the **even** order **bordered** magic squares. In some cases, we have to use fractional numbers to reach minimum perfect square sum of entries. For more study on **bordered** magic squares refer H. White's web-site [3].

The idea of bordered magic squares is already discussed by H. White's web-site [3] where the borders are of **single digits**. Borders multiples of even numbers starting from order 4 are done extensively by author [25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30].

1.1 Summary of Bordered Magic Squares

1.1.1 Odd Numbers Multiples

- **Single Digit:** Bordered magic squares based on single digit [11, 12, 3].
- **Three Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 3 [30].
- **Five Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 5 [32].
- **Seven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 7 [34].
- **Nine Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 9 [36].
- **Eleven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 11 [38].
- **Thirteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 13 [40].
- **Fifteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 15 [42].
- **Seventeen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 17 [44].
- **Nineteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 19 [46].

1.1.2 Even Numbers Multiples

- **Two Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic rectangles multiples of 2 [74, 75, 76, 77, 77, 78, 79].
- **Four Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 4 [25, 31].
- **Six Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 6 [26, 33].
- **Eight Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 8 [27, 35].
- **Ten Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 10 [28, 37].
- **Twelve Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 12 [29, 39].
- **Fourteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 14 [41].
- **Sixteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 16 [43].
- **Eighteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 18 [45].
- **Twenty Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 20 [47].

The advantage in working with even number multiples is that we can work with equal sums blocks of magic squares.

The aim of this work is to bring multiple order **bordered** magic squares of orders 20, 30, 42, 56, 72, 90, 108 and 112. Let see below how it is done.

See below the details of above multiple order bordered magic square.

• **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**

1. Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.

• **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**

1. In this case, we have considered two types of magic squares of order 4.

(a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4.

(b) The second is formed by two equal sums magic sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 resulting in a magic square of order 4. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 20

• **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**

1. In this case, we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 5.

(a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5.

(b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 5, where there are two **equal sums magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner.

(c) The third is **single-layer bordered** magic square with magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 30

• **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**

1. In this case also we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 6.

(a) The first is normal magic square of order 6.

(b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 6, where there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner with two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

(c) The third one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 42

• **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**

1. In this case, we have considered 5 different types of magic squares of order 7.

(a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7.

(b) The second is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle and 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 .

(c) The third is a **cornered** magic square of order 7 composed of another **cornered** magic square of order 5 with magic squares of order 3 at the upper-left corner. Two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 .

(d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 with magic square of order 3 in the middle. Also there are four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 . This type of magic squares we call as **cyclic-double-layer** magic square of order 7.

(e) The fifth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 56.

• **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 8.

(a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 formed by four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.

(b) The second is a **cornered** magic square of order 8, where there is again a **cornered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×6 are of equal sums in each case.

(c) The third is a **double-layer bordered** magic square with **pandiagonal** with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. It has 2 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×8 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

(d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 with a magic square of order 4 in the middle. This magic square of order 4 is again composed two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . The magic square of order 4 also have four equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×6 . Since it is formed by only **strips** of equal width, we call it a **striped** magic square of order 8.

(e) The fifth one is four equal sums magic squares of order 4, where each magic square of order 4 is formed by two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . Since it is formed by only magic rectangles of equal width it is known as **striped** magic square.

(f) The sixth one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic square of order 72.

• **6th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 9**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9.

(a) The first is composed of 9 **semi-magic** squares of order 3 resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9.

(b) The second is a cornered magic square, where magic squares of orders 7 and 5 are also **cornered** magic squares at the upper-left corner having magic square of order 3.

(c) The third is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 having **cornered** magic square of order 5 in the middle. Two **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 and two **magic rectangles** of orders 2×5 are of equal sums in each case.

(d) The forth is again a **double-layer bordered** with **single-layer** bordered magic square of order 5 at the middle. The external border is composed of 2 **magic rectangles** of order 2×9 and two **magic rectangles** of order 2×5 . Both are of equal sums in each case. In the middle there is a magic square of order 3.

(e) The fifth is again a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 with external bordered as 4 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×7 . In the middle there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. This kind of magic square we call as **cyclic-type double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9

(f) The sixth is a normal **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 having magic square of order 3 in the middle.

• **7th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 10**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 10.

(a) First one is a **traditional** magic square of order 10.

(b) The second one is a **cornered** magic square of order 10, where magic squares of orders 8 and 6 are also **cornered** magic squares at the upper-left corner having magic square of order 4.

(c) The third is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 10 having **single-layer** magic square of order 6 in the middle. Four magic rectangles of order 2×8 are of equal sums magic sums. This kind of magic square we call as **cyclic-double-layer bordered** magic square of order 10.

(d) The fourth one is again a **double-layer bordered** with **cornered** magic squares of order 6 in the middle. It contains magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. The external border is composed of 2 **magic rectangles** of order 2×10 and two **magic rectangles** of order 2×6 . Both are of equal sums in each case.

(e) The fifth one is again a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 10 embedded with a **striped** magic square of order 8 composed 4 equal sums magic squares of order 4 or 8 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 .

(f) The sixth is a normal **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 10 having magic square of order 4 in the middle.

• **8th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 11**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 11.

(a) First one is a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 11 with magic square of order 3 is in the middle. The 4 magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 4 magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal magic sums in each case.

(b) The second one is a **cornered** magic square of order 11, where magic squares of orders 9, 7 and 5 are also **cornered** at the upper-left corner with magic square of order 3. The 2 magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , 2 of order 2×5 , 2 of order 2×7 and 2 of order 2×9 are of equal sums in each case.

(c) The third one is again a **double-layer bordered** magic squares of orders 11 and 7 having magic square of order 3 in the middle. In this case the 2 magic rectangles of orders 2×11 , 4 of order 2×7 and 2 of order 2×3 are of equal magic sums in each case. These types of magic squares sometimes we call as **flat-double-layer bordered** magic squares.

(d) The fourth is a **cyclic-double-layer bordered** with magic square of order 3 in the middle. The 4 magic rectangles of order 2×9 and 4 of order 2×5 are of equal sums in each case.

(e) The fifth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a magic square of order 9 composed of 9 equal sums magic squares of order 3.

(f) The sixth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 11 having magic square of order 3 in the middle.

- **9th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 6 and a Magic Rectangle of Order 6x12**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 6.

- (a) The first is a magic square is a normal magic square of order 6 without any special properties.
- (b) The second is a **cornered** magic square of order 6, where there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper left corner. The two magic rectangles of order 2×4 are of equal sums only in width. In length, 2×6 are of equal sums.
- (c) The third is a **striped** magic square of order order 6. It composed of a magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and 2×4 . The three magic rectangles of order 2×4 are of equal sums. When a magic square composed of only magic rectangles of equal width, we call it as striped magic squares.
- (d) The forth is a single-layer bordered magic square of order 6 embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle.
- (e) The fifth magic square of order 6 is composed of one **single-layer bordered** magic rectangle of order 2×6 and two simples rows of order 1×6 .
- (f) The last one is a **single-layer bordered** magic rectangle of order 6×12 .

Below summarises the construction levels.

- **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**

- Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.

- **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**

- In this case we have considered two different types of magic squares of order 4. Combining with magic square of order 12 we have **2-different types** of magic squares of order 20.

- **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**

- In this case, we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 5. Combining with 3 magic squares of order 20 we have **6-different types** of magic squares of order 20.

- **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**

- In this case also we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 6. Combining with 6 magic squares of order 30 we have **18-different types** of magic squares of order 42.

- **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**

- In this case, we have considered 5-different ways of magic squares of order 7. Combining with 18 magic squares of order 42 we have **90-different types** of magic squares of order 56.

- **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**

- In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares. Combining with 90 magic squares of order 56 we have **540-different types** of magic squares of order 72.
- **6th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 9**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9. Combining with 540 magic squares of order 90 we have $6 \times 540 = 3240$, i.e., **3240-different types** of magic squares of order 90.
- **7th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 10**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 10. Combining with 3240 magic squares of order 90 we have $6 \times 3240 = 19440$, i.e., **19440-different types** of magic squares of order 110.
- **8th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 11**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 11. Combining with 19440 magic squares of order 90 we have $6 \times 19440 = 116640$, i.e., **116640-different types** of magic squares of order 132.
- **9th Border: Different or Equal sums magic squares of order 6 and a Magic Rectangle of Order 6x12**
 - In this case we have considered again 6 different types of magic squares of order 6. Combining with 3888 magic squares of order 6, we get $116640 \times 6 = 699840$ magic squares of order 144. This number is too high, we have considered only 648 magic square of order 132. This lead us to $648 \times 6 = 3888$ multiple order **bordered** magic squares of order 144.

The total count at each level equals the product of all variant counts up to that level:

$$N_{\text{ord.144}} = 1(3) \times 2(4) \times 3(5) \times 3(6) \times 5(7) \times 6(8) \times 6(9) \times 6(10) \times 6(11) \times 6(6) = 699840. \quad (2)$$

More details of last border i.e., 8th border of magic squares of order 12 are given section below.

2 Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 144

In order to get **bordered magic squares** of order 144, we shall use the following six different types of magic squares of order 12 over the magic square of order 120 as an upper border magic squares resulting in magic squares of order 144.

6 mgc		111	6 mgc		111								
1	35	34	33	2	6	111	17	22	11	24	29	8	111
30	8	28	9	11	25	111	12	23	18	21	27	10	111
24	23	15	16	20	13	111	26	13	20	15	35	2	111
18	14	21	22	17	19	111	19	16	25	14	9	28	111
7	26	10	27	29	12	111	4	3	36	30	6	32	111
31	5	3	4	32	36	111	33	34	1	7	5	31	111
1	111	111	111	111	111	111	2	111	111	111	111	111	111
6 mgc		111	6 mgc		111								
11	26	6	31	3	34	111	32	30	3	36	4	6	111
28	9	29	8	36	1	111	2	17	22	11	24	35	111
10	27	32	5	2	35	111	8	12	23	18	21	29	111
25	12	7	30	33	4	111	10	26	13	20	15	27	111
21	13	20	19	15	23	111	28	19	16	25	14	9	111
16	24	17	18	22	14	111	31	7	34	1	33	5	111
3	111	111	111	111	111	111	4	111	111	111	111	111	111

6		111																	
24	17	22	16	14	18	111	14	57	2	9	7	58	69	65	13	68	70	6	438
7	31	5	33	34	1	111	1	56	25	19	20	51	28	18	47	49	52	72	438
29	27	9	12	26	8	111	62	23	33	38	30	44	36	39	41	31	50	11	438
2	10	28	25	11	35	111	63	46	40	35	43	29	37	34	32	42	27	10	438
36	6	32	4	3	30	111	12	21	48	54	53	22	45	55	26	24	17	61	438
13	20	15	21	23	19	111	67	16	71	64	66	15	4	8	60	5	3	59	438
5	111	111	111	111	111	111	219	219	219	219	219	219	219	219	219	219	219	219	219

See the details:

- In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9.
 1. The first is a magic square is a normal magic square of order 6 without any special properties.
 2. The second is a **cornered** magic square of order 6, where there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order

- 4 at the upper left corner. The two magic rectangles of order 2×4 are of equal sums only in width. In length, 2×6 are of equal sums.
3. The third is a **striped** magic square of order order 6. It composed of a magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and 2×4 . The three magic rectangles of order 2×4 are of equal sums. When a magic square composed of only magic rectangles of equal width, we call it as striped magic squares.
 4. The forth is a single-layer bordered magic square of order 6 embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle.
 5. The fifth magic square of order 6 is composed of one **single-layer bordered** magic rectangle of order 2×6 and two simples rows of order 1×6 .
 6. The last one is a **single-layer bordered** magic rectangle of order 6×12 .

Combining with 3240 magic squares of order 90 we have $6 \times 3240 = 19940$, i.e., **19940-different types** of magic squares of order 108. Since this number is too high, we worked with 648 magic squares of order 90, resulting in 3888 magic square of order 108.

Above there are only few examples, but there are 3888 magic squares of order 144 composed of magic squares orders 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 6. More details are in an **excel files** attached with the work.

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